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Investigation of the Correlation Between the Bitcoin Price and Tortilla Prices in Mexico

ICBBPTPM

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the final Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Investigation of the Correlation Between the Bitcoin Price and Tortilla Prices in Mexico project, delivered in April 2024. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the FAIR data section.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Dennis Leser acts as the data manager who is in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

This project re-use the "Tortilla prices in Mexico" dataset (< 20 MB) from <https://www.kaggle.com> (creator: Rick Chavelas; license: CC0: Public Domain), which contains the tortilla prices per kilogram in Mexican Peso (start date = "2007-01-10"; end date = "2024-03-01") for big retail stores and mom-and-pop stores for various states and cities in Mexico. Furthermore, at the begin of the project, the daily Bitcoin price data (< 500 KB) and daily exchange rates data (< 500 KB) between Mexican Peso (MXN) and US dollar (USD) was downloaded from <https://finance.yahoo.com/> on the 19th of March, 2024 (start date = "2007-01-10"; end date = "2024-02-28") and saved in the csv files yahoo_bitcoin_data_2024-03-19.csv and yahoo_ex_rates_data_2024-03-19.csv. This step is not necessary to reproduce the results of this project, because the corresponding datasets are saved in the GitHub repository.

During the project, the exchange rates data were used to convert the tortilla price data in Mexican Peso (MXN) into US dollar (USD). The tortilla prices per kilogram from the "Tortilla prices in Mexico" dataset (converted into US dollar) and the closing prices from the daily Bitcoin price data (in US dollar) were used to calculate the Spearman correlation coefficients between the daily closing prices of Bitcoin (start date = "2014-09-17"; end date = "2024-02-27") and the mean tortilla prices (start date = "2014-09-17"; end date = "2024-02-27") for various states of Mexico (aggregated over the prices per cities in the corresponding state) as well as separated for big retail stores and mom-and-pop stores.

These Spearman correlation coefficients were saved into the csv file results_spearman_corr.csv, which are the output data of this project (< 10 KB).

The output data of this project could be entertaining for people, who likes statistics, but is not really useful for economic or academic purposes (maybe for education).

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	results_spearman_corr.csv	Structured text	CSV	100 MB	no
P2	yahoo_bitcoin_data_2024-03-19.csv	Structured text	CSV	100 MB	no
P3	yahoo_ex_rates_data_2024-03-19.csv	Structured text	CSV	100 MB	no

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Tortilla prices in Mexico	https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/richave/tortilla-prices-in-mexico	CC0: Public Domain	no

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The project was implemented in Python 3.7 in a Jupyter Notebook. To download the daily Bitcoin data and the daily exchange rates data from <https://finance.yahoo.com/>, the Python packages pandas_datareader and yfinance were used. All datasets are in csv format. For reading and writing the csv files, the Python package pandas was used. The Python package matplotlib was used to create additional plots.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Students and general public

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

The used and produced data were made findable, by uploading it to a repository on GitHub that provides a persistent identifier (DOI). For all datasets in the corresponding GitHub repository are metadata files with the name <dataset_name>-metadata.json available. These metadata files (tortilla_prices-metadata.json, yahoo_bitcoin_data_2024-03-19-metadata.json, yahoo_ex_rates_data_2024-03-19-metadata.json and results_spearman_corr-metadata.json) follow the CSVW Namespace Vocabulary Terms for metadata from W3C and contains common metadata such as title, description and datatype. The explanation of the CSVW Namespace Vocabulary Terms for metadata can be found at <https://www.w3.org/ns/csvw>. This CSVW Namespace Vocabulary Terms for metadata allows inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability and helps others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We made all our data accessible by providing open access to data via a GitHub repository, which is licensed with MIT.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	no	2024-02-29	GitHub	10.5281/zenodo.11080415	CC-BY-4.0
P2	Open	no	2024-02-29	GitHub	10.5281/zenodo.11080415	CC-BY-4.0
P3	Open	no	2024-02-29	GitHub	10.5281/zenodo.11080415	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

The corresponding GitHub repository can be found at <https://github.com/dleser93/Investigation-of-the-Correlation-Between-the-Bitcoin-Price-and-Tortilla-Prices-in-Mexico> and contains a digital object identifier (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11080415), the Jupyter Notebook file "Spearman_Corr_Bitcoin_Tortilla.ipynb", which contains the documentation and the code of the project. Furthermore, it contains a Readme file, a LICENSE file as well as the two subfolder "data" and "results". The subfolder "data" contains the input datasets (tortilla_prices.csv, yahoo_bitcoin_data_2024-03-19.csv and yahoo_ex_rates_data_2024-03-19.csv) and their metadata files. The subfolder "results" contains the output dataset (results_spearman_corr.csv) of the project and its metadata file.

Methods or software needed to access and use data:

To access and use the data from the GitHub repository, Python, access to GitHub, Jupyter Notebook, and the Python packages pandas (implies numpy) and matplotlib are necessary.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow re-using, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We made our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. For example, the financial datasets `yahoo_bitcoin_data_2024-03-19.csv` and `yahoo_ex_rates_data_2024-03-19.csv` follows the standard practices in finance (for example the column names of the csv files: Open, Close, Low, High, etc.). Also, the storage format CSV is widely used in all domains.

The metadata files follow the CSVW Namespace Vocabulary Terms for metadata from W3C and contains common metadata such as title, description, and datatype. The explanation of the CSVW Namespace Vocabulary Terms for metadata can be found at <https://www.w3.org/ns/csvw>. This CSVW Namespace Vocabulary Terms for metadata allows inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability and helps others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We made our data reusable by adding metadata to all published datasets and a comprehensive Readme file in the GitHub repository.

The Jupyter Notebook file can be also seen like a documentation of the data analysis and includes details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information.

Furthermore, the Readme file in the GitHub repository provides an overview of this project. The MIT license of the GitHub repository allows free access for the project code and the used data.

For data quality checks, peer review of the data was done by Dennis Leser at the begin of the project.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

...

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0

During the project, the data manager Dennis Leser produced metadata files, did day-to-day cross-checks, back-ups and other quality control activities. Furthermore, Dennis Leser was responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

All datasets, metadata files, the project documentation and the project code are public available in a GitHub repository, which doesn't produce costs to make the project data FAIR.

This GitHub repository contains the digital object identifier (DOI): 10.5281/zenodo.11080415. The data for the project is organized into subfolders. The input datasets (tortilla_prices.csv, yahoo_bitcoin_data_2024-03-19.csv and yahoo_ex_rates_data_2024-03-19.csv) together with their metadata files are saved in the subfolder "data". All output datasets (results_spearman_corr.csv) together with their metadata files are saved in the subfolder "results".

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the data manager Dennis Leser.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

This project doesn't process any sensitive data.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
P2	writing	writing	reading only
P3	writing	writing	reading only
R1	writing	writing	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	GitHub	10 years
P2	GitHub	10 years
P3	GitHub	10 years
R1	GitHub	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

This project doesn't process any personal data.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

6.3. Ethical issues

This project doesn't contain ethical issues with the used or produced.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?